

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some Haloanilido Pyrazoline and Isoxazoline Derivatives

N. K. MANDAL, R. SINHA and K. P. BANERJEE*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

Haloacetoacetanilide on condensation with aromatic aldehyde yielded the corresponding haloanilido α,β -unsaturated ketones which on heating with hydrazine hydrate/phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the corresponding haloanilido pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives. The biological activities of the compounds were evaluated.

A perusal of the literature¹⁻⁵ on pyrazolines and isoxazolines has revealed that these compounds are not only used in textile and cinematographic film industry but they also show widely differing biological activities as bactericides, insecticides, fungicides, anaesthetics, analgesics and antidiabetic agents. Amino compounds, in general, are well

known for their manifold physiological actions. Again, the presence of halogen atoms in a compound is known to have an activity-enhancing effect. Considering all these factors, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a few haloanilido pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives (Scheme 1) and to evaluate their biological action.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

Aceto-o-chloroacetanilide (I): A mixture of *o*-chloroaniline (0.01 mol) and ethylacetoacetate (0.01 mol) was heated to 130° for 1.5 h. On cooling, the colourless crystals of **I** were separated. It was filtered off and then recrystallised from ethanol to yield the product (65%), m.p. 102°.

3-(o-Chloroanilido)-4-aryl-but-3-en-2-one (II): A mixture of **I** (0.01 mol) and an aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) was fused for 0.25 h and the resulting mass was cooled and treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The product was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield **II**. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3-HALOANILIDO-4-ARYL-BUT-3-EN-2-ONE (II)

Compd. no.	X	R	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %
IIa	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	159	Yellow	56
IIb	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	165	Yellow	52
IIc	<i>o</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	144	Yellow	57
IIc	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	164	Yellow	54
IIe	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	142	Brown	65
IIc	<i>p</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	152	Yellow	59
IIg	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	162	Yellow	67
IIh	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	139	Yellow	85
III	<i>p</i> -Br	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	198	Yellow	70

All compounds gave satisfactory (C, H) elemental analyses.

N-Acetyl-3-methyl-4-(o-chloroanilido)-5-arylpyrazolines (III): A mixture of *o*-chloroanilido- α,β -unsaturated ketone (**II**), hydrazinehydrate (0.015 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solution was concentrated, cooled and poured over ice-water when product **III** was separated which was filtered and crystallised from a mixture of ethanol-petroleum ether (1 : 1). The results are incorporated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—N-ACETYL-3-METHYL-4-HALOANILIDO-5-ARYL-PYRAZOLINE (III)

Compd. no.	X	R	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %
IIIa	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	110	Red	72
IIIb	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	96	Red	65
IIIc	<i>o</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	71	Red	59
IIIc	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	141	Yellow	52
IIIe	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	187	Red	62
IIIc	<i>p</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	216	Yellow	52
IIIg	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	201	Red	85
IIIh	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	176	Yellow	62
IIIh	<i>p</i> -Br	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	187	Yellow	71

All compounds gave satisfactory (C, H) elemental analyses.

N-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(o-chloroanilido)-5-arylpyrazolines (IV): A mixture of *o*-chloroanilido- α,β -unsaturated ketone (**II**), phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed

for 9 h. The resulting mixture was concentrated, cooled and then poured onto acidified ice-water. Coloured compounds were separated which were filtered and crystallised from ethanol-petroleum ether (1 : 3). The results are incorporated in Table 3.

TABLE 3—N-PHENYL-3-METHYL-4-HALOANILIDO-5-ARYL-PYRAZOLINE (IV)

Compd. no.	X	R	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %
IVa	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	126	Red	75
IVb	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	97	Red	71
IVc	<i>o</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	94	Red	65
IVd	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	98	Reddish brown	65
IVe	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	138	Reddish yellow	75
IVf	<i>p</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	110	Red	72
IVg	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	81	Yellow	81
IVh	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	74	Reddish yellow	72
IVI	<i>p</i> -Br	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	66	Red	81

All compounds gave satisfactory (C, H) elemental analyses.

3-Methyl-4-(o-chloroanilido)-5-aryl-isoxazoline (V): A mixture of *o*-chloroanilido- α,β -unsaturated ketone (**II**, 0.01 mol) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.015 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and KOH (0.015 mol) was refluxed for 10 h. The resulting mixture was concentrated, cooled and then poured onto ice-water. The compound **V** was filtered and crystallised with ethanol-petroleum ether (1 : 3). The results are incorporated in Table 4.

TABLE 4—3-METHYL-4-HALOANILIDO-5-ARYL-ISOXAZOLINE (V)

Compd. no.	X	R	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %
Va	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	121	Red	64
Vb	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	102	Reddish yellow	62
Vc	<i>o</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	95	Red	62
Vd	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	82	Red	61
Ve	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	185	Red	45
Vf	<i>p</i> -Cl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	186	Reddish yellow	71
Vg	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	110	Yellow	61
Vh	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄	110	Yellow	82
VI	<i>p</i> -Br	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄	183	Yellow	51

All compounds gave satisfactory (C, H) elemental analyses.

Biological screening of some pyrazoline derivatives:

Biological screening of some pyrazoline derivatives was done following the method of Verma and Nobles⁶ and the results are recorded in Table 5.

Results and Discussion

The haloanilido- α,β -unsaturated ketones (**II**), prepared by the condensation of halogenoacetanilide with aldehydes, showed absorption bands at 1690 (conjugated CO), 1600 (olefinic double bond)

TABLE 5—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF SOME HALOANILIDO PYRAZOLINES

Compd no.	<i>B. Subtilis</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>Xanthromonus citri</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>
IVa	++	-	+	-
IVb	-	-	-	++
IVc	-	-	++	-
IIIb	+	+	-	+
Tetracycline	+++	++++	+++	+++

Inhibition zone size: + = 6-12, ++ = 12-18, +++ = 18-24, ++++ = 24-30, +++++ = > 30 mm
 - = No inhibition.

and 3320 cm^{-1} (NH). Ketones (II), when heated with hydrazine and phenylhydrazine, the corresponding haloanilido pyrazolines III and IV were directly obtained, obviously, via the initial formation of hydrazone and phenylhydrazone derivatives which cyclise under the experimental conditions. The formation of these pyrazolines was confirmed by their positive Knorr's colour test⁷ which is a characteristic test for aryl pyrazolines. The structures of III and IV were fully corroborated by ir spectral data which showed absorption at 1660 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1600 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 3320 (NH) and 1230 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$). Similarly, ketones (II), on heating with hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielded the corresponding haloanilido isoxazolines (V), which showed ir absorption at 1600 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1660 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and 3320 cm^{-1} (NH).

The biological activity of some representative compounds was initially tested and it was found that the compound IVa showed activity against *B.*

subtilis, IVc against *Xanthromonus citri* and IVb against *B. pumilus*. The results of the screened compounds showed 66% inhibition effect towards some specific organisms, taking tetracycline as the standard (100%). It may be seen from Table 5 that *N*-phenylhaloanilido pyrazoline derivatives are more active than their corresponding *N*-acylhaloanilido counterparts and probably the position of the substituent in aryl ring attached to pyrazoline nucleus may have some influence for exhibiting different activity on different organisms. The present screening, however, does not permit to draw a general conclusion and work is in progress on these lines.

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